

METHODS AND TECHNIQUES OF TEACHING RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: The article presents the results of an analysis of the methods of teaching the Russian language. This material will be useful for improving courses on the theory and history of methods of teaching the Russian language, and will help Russian language teachers to update the classical ideas of the method.

Key words: Learning process, information-receptive method, reproductive method, mastery of knowledge, skills, desire of the student, subject, practical, intellectual and emotional means, a number of classifications, verbal methods, story, relevance, heuristic conversation, introductory or introductory, discussion, lecture, review, note-taking, exercise, visual methods, illustrative and demonstration, use of visual teaching methods, inductive and deductive methods.

Introduction. Learning is a process the course of which is subject to a certain logic, which means it can be studied, controlled and predicted. The learning process is otherwise called the educational or didactic process.

The social orientation of learning is manifested in the fact that learning is one of the optimal ways of human social adaptation, i.e. preparing a person for life in society.

Today there are many definitions of teaching methods. However, given the diversity of definitions, it is necessary to understand the method as a derivative of the teaching model, type of training, and direction of training. Our working definition of the method will be the following: a teaching method is a way of interaction between a teacher and students, in which mastery of knowledge,

abilities, skills is achieved, the worldview of students is formed, and their abilities are developed. Teaching is a purposeful process in which the teacher helps the student to internalize the social experience of society. Methods are a very important element of this process. Experience is embodied in the content of education - in standards, programs, educational complexes. Mastering the content of education is the goal of learning, methods are the way to achieve this goal. The method consists of sequential actions aimed at achieving a goal. The student in the learning process, on the one hand, is the object of learning, on the other, the subject of learning. In order for a teacher to succeed, the student's desire is necessary; his goal must coincide with the teacher's goal. In addition, a teacher can only set a goal and fill the necessary methods of activity with the necessary content if he is to some extent aware of the individual properties of students, the general features of the process of mastering material as a mechanism for moving an object towards a goal. Knowing the purpose and features of the process of mastering the material, the teacher outlines and carries out activities using the subject, practical, intellectual and emotional means available to him, evokes the student's goal corresponding to them, as a result of which he carries out his actions using the means available to him. The student's activity sets in motion the mechanism of assimilation of the material, due to which the student himself changes and the learning goal is more or less close to the desired achievement. Without achieving the goal, it is impossible to talk about a successful method. This is the sustainable achievement of a goal in an optimal time frame with less effort. The structure of the teaching method One of the acute problems of modern didactics is the problem of classifying teaching methods. Currently there is no single point of view on this issue. Due to the fact that different authors base the division of teaching methods into groups and subgroups on different criteria, there are a number of classifications. The earliest classification is the division of teaching methods into teacher methods (story, explanation, conversation) and student work methods (exercises, independent work). From the beginning of the 30s of the 20th century

to the present day, the classification of methods “according to the source of knowledge acquisition” is considered the most common, and when applied to the

Russian language it is presented as follows:

- 1) verbal methods - the source of knowledge is the spoken or printed word;
- 2) practical methods - students gain knowledge and develop skills by performing practical actions;
- 3) visual methods - the source of knowledge is observed objects, phenomena, visual aids.

Verbal methods occupy a leading place in this classification of teaching methods. There were periods when they were almost the only way to transfer knowledge. Progressive teachers (Ya. A. Komensky, K. D. Ushinsky, etc.) The activities of the teacher, the goal of the teacher, the means of the teacher, the actions of the student, the goal of the student, the means of the student, the mechanism of the student’s movement towards the goal. The product of assimilation, the achieved goal, opposed the absolutization of their meaning, argued for the need to supplement them with visual and practical methods. Currently, they are often called obsolete, “inactive”. The evaluation of this group of methods must be approached objectively.

Verbal methods make it possible to convey a large amount of information in the shortest possible time, pose problems to students and indicate ways to solve them. With the help of words, a teacher can evoke in the minds of children vivid pictures of the past, present and future of humanity. The word activates the imagination, memory, and feelings of students. Verbal methods are divided into the following types. A story is an oral narrative presentation of the content of educational material (used at all stages of school education). A number of pedagogical requirements are usually imposed on the story as a method of presenting new knowledge;

in particular, the story should:

- ensure the ideological and moral orientation of teaching;

- contain only reliable and scientifically verified facts;
- include a sufficient number of vivid and convincing examples and facts proving the correctness of the proposed provisions;
- have a clear logic of presentation;
- be emotional;
- presented in simple and accessible language;
- reflect elements of the teacher's personal assessment and attitude to the facts and events presented.

Explanation verbal interpretation of patterns, essential properties of the object of study, individual concepts, phenomena. Like a story, an explanation is a monologue form of presentation. Explanation is most often resorted to when studying the theoretical material of various sciences.

Using the explanation method requires:

- precise and clear formulation of the task, the essence of the problem, the question;
- consistent disclosure of cause-and-effect relationships, reasoning and evidence;
- use of comparison, juxtaposition, analogy;
- attracting bright examples;
- impeccable logic of presentation.

Explanation as a teaching method is widely used in working with children of different age groups. However, in middle and high school age, due to the complexity of educational material and the increasing intellectual capabilities of students, the use of this method becomes more necessary than when working with younger students.

Conversation is a dialogical teaching method in which the teacher, by posing a carefully thought-out system of questions, leads students to understand new material or checks their understanding of what has already been learned. Conversation is one of the oldest methods of didactic work. Depending on the

specific tasks, the content of the educational material, the level of creative cognitive activity of students, and the place of conversation in the didactic process, different types of conversations are distinguished. Heuristic conversation is widespread.

During a heuristic conversation, the teacher, relying on the students' existing knowledge and practical experience, leads them to understand and assimilate new knowledge, formulate rules and conclusions. Informative conversations are used to communicate new knowledge. If a conversation precedes the study of new material, it is called introductory or introductory. The purpose of such a conversation is to induce in students a state of readiness to learn new things. Consolidating conversations are used after learning new material. During the conversation, questions can be addressed to one student (individual conversation) or by students of the whole class (frontal conversation). One type of conversation is an interview. It can be carried out both with the class as a whole and with individual groups of students. It is especially useful to organize an interview in high school, when students show more independence in judgment, can pose problematic questions, and express their opinions on certain topics put up for discussion by the teacher. In addition, an interview is a good means of identifying students' basic knowledge. The success of conversations largely depends on the correctness of asking questions. Questions are asked by the teacher to the whole class so that all students are prepared to answer. Questions should be short, clear, meaningful, and formulated in such a way as to stimulate the student's thoughts. You should not ask questions that suggest or lead you to guess the answer. You should not formulate alternative questions that require clear answers like "yes" or "no".

In general, the conversation method has the following advantages:

- activates the cognitive activity of students;
- develops their memory and speech;
- has great educational power;

- is a good diagnostic tool. Disadvantages of the conversation method:
- requires a lot of time and sufficient knowledge of students;
- contains an element of risk (a student may give an incorrect answer, which is perceived by other students and recorded in their memory);

Discussion is an exchange of views on a particular issue, and these views reflect the participants' own opinions or are based on the opinions of others. This method is advisable to use when students have a significant degree of maturity and independent thinking and are able to justify their point of view. A well-conducted discussion has great educational and educational value: it teaches a deeper understanding of the problem, the ability to defend one's position, and take into account the opinions of others.

A lecture is a monologue way of presenting voluminous material. It is used, as a rule, in high school and takes up the entire or almost the entire lesson. The advantage of a lecture is the ability to ensure the completeness and integrity of students' perception of educational material in its logical relationships on the topic as a whole. The relevance of using lectures in modern conditions is increasing due to the use of block study of new educational material on topics or large sections. A school lecture can also be used to review the material covered. Such lectures are called review lectures. They are conducted on one or several topics to summarize and systematize the material studied. The use of lectures as a teaching method in a modern school allows one to significantly intensify the cognitive activity of students, to involve them in independent searches for additional scientific information to solve problematic educational and cognitive tasks, complete thematic assignments, conduct independent experiments and experiments bordering on research activities. This explains the fact that the share of lectures in high schools has recently begun to increase. The most important verbal learning method is working with a book. In primary school, work with books is carried out mainly in lessons under the guidance of a teacher. In the future, schoolchildren

increasingly learn to work with the book independently. There are a number of techniques for working independently with printed sources.

The main ones:

- note-taking - a summary, a brief recording of the content of what was read. Note-taking is done in the first (oneself) or third person. Taking notes in the first person better develops independent thinking;
- drawing up a text plan. The plan can be simple or complex. To draw up a plan, after reading the text, you need to break it into parts and title each part;
- thesis - a brief summary of the main ideas of what was read;
- quotation - verbatim excerpt from the text. The output data must be indicated (author, title of the work, place of publication, publisher, year of publication, page);
- annotation - a brief condensed summary of the content of what was read without loss of essential meaning;
- reviewing - writing a short review expressing your attitude about what you read;
- drawing up a certificate - information about something obtained after a search. Information can be biographical, terminological, or geographical;
- drawing up a formal logical model - a verbal and schematic image of what has been read;
- compiling a thematic thesaurus - an ordered set of basic concepts by section, topic;
- drawing up a matrix of ideas - comparative characteristics of similar objects, phenomena in the works of different authors.

Practical methods are based on the practical activities of students. The main practical method is to do exercises.

Exercise is the repeated (multiple) performance of a mental or practical action in order to master it or improve its quality. The nature and methodology of the exercises depends on the characteristics of the subject, the specific material, the

issue being studied and the age of the students. According to the degree of independence of students, exercises are distinguished:

- reproducing (exercises to reproduce what is known for the purpose of consolidation);
- training (exercises on applying knowledge in new conditions);
- commented (exercises with comments on upcoming operations - to detect typical errors, correct student actions; the student gives the comment).

Exercises by nature are divided into:

- oral (promote the development of logical thinking, memory, speech, attention of students; they are dynamic and do not require significant time spent on taking notes);
- written (used to consolidate knowledge and develop skills in its application);
- contribute to the development of logical thinking, written language culture, independence in work);

Exercise requirements:

- students' conscious approach to exercises;
- compliance with the didactic sequence in performing exercises from memorizing and memorizing educational material through the reproduction and application of previously learned to the independent transfer of what has been learned to non-standard situations, that is, its creative application in practical activities.

Practical methods also include practical work that is carried out after studying large sections, the topics of which are general in nature.

Visual methods are methods in which the assimilation of educational material depends on the visual aids and technical means used in the learning process.

There is an illustration method (showing students illustrative aids: posters, tables, paintings) and a demonstration method (demonstration of experiments,

films, excerpts from film magazines, cartoons, fairy tales). This division of visual aids into illustrative and demonstrative is conditional. It does not exclude the possibility of classifying certain visual aids as both illustrative and demonstrative. (For example, showing illustrations through a television screen). The introduction of new technical means into the educational process (television, VCRs, computers) expands the possibilities of visual teaching methods.

When using visual teaching methods, a number of conditions must be met:

- the visualization used must be appropriate for the age of the students;
- visuals should be used in moderation, and should be shown only at the appropriate moment in the lesson;
- observation should be organized in such a way that all students can clearly see the object being demonstrated;
- it is necessary to clearly highlight the main, essential things when showing illustrations;
- it is necessary to think through in detail the explanations for the phenomenon being demonstrated;
- visibility must be clearly consistent with the content of the material;
- it is necessary to involve the students themselves in finding the desired information in the visual aid.

The following classification - classification of methods according to the nature of students' cognitive activity includes 5 methods.

Information-receptive (explanatory-illustrative) - a method consisting in the presentation of ready-made information by the teacher and its assimilation by students.

Reproductive - a method that involves the organization of reproduction, reproducing methods of activity that the teacher reported earlier and a sample of which he showed (solving typical problems, exercises, retelling texts on the teacher's instructions).

The method of problem presentation is a method that involves the teacher posing a problem; the teacher himself solves this problem, but certainly demonstrates the contradictory ways of the process of cognition itself, illustrating the culture of thinking in the course of solving the problem.

Partial search (heuristic) method is a method that assumes initial mastery by students of individual elements of search activity (for example, the teacher poses a problem, students put forward only a hypothesis, or the teacher presents facts and students draw conclusions).

Research is a method that involves the teacher organizing creative search activities of students by posing new problems and problematic tasks for them. The teacher creates these problem situations himself during the educational process, but arranges them in a row according to the degree of increasing complexity and accessibility. Students solve the problem themselves, carrying out all the known stages of research:

- observation and study of facts and phenomena; clarifying what is unclear, posing a problem;
- putting forward hypotheses;
- drawing up a research plan;
- establishing connections between the phenomena being studied and others (testing the hypothesis);
- formulating a decision;
- checking the solution;
- determination of the meaning of the acquired knowledge, its possible and necessary application.

In the process of solving a problem, students discover the ability to use knowledge and skills in a new situation, alternative thinking and vision of new problems appear. Summarizing what has been said, we present the characteristics of each method from the perspective of the activities of the teacher and student.

There is also a classification of methods according to the method of supplying the material. There are inductive and deductive methods that take into account the logic of cognition and psychological assimilation. Inductive and deductive teaching methods characterize an extremely important feature of the methods - the ability to reveal the logic of movement of the content of educational material. The use of inductive or deductive methods means choosing a certain logic for revealing the content of the topic under study - from particular to general or from general to particular.

Inductive method. Inductive study of a topic is especially useful in cases where the material is primarily factual in nature or is associated with the formation of concepts, the meaning of which can only become clear through inductive reasoning. Inductive methods are widely applicable when performing practical tasks. The weakness of inductive teaching methods is that they require more time to learn new material than deductive ones. They contribute to the development of abstract thinking to a lesser extent, since they are based on concrete facts, experiences and other data.

Deductive method. The deductive method promotes faster mastery of educational material and more actively develops abstract thinking.

Research method. Drawing up and presenting problematic tasks to find solutions. Monitoring the progress of the decision. Perception of a problem or independent perception of a problem. Understanding the conditions of the problem. Planning the stages of research (solutions) and research methods at each stage. Self-control during the research process and its completion. Predominance of involuntary memorization.

Reproduction of the research process, motivation of its results. Its use is especially useful when studying theoretical material, when solving problems that require identifying consequences from some more general provisions. When using inductive and deductive teaching methods, the previously described verbal, visual and practical methods are used, as well as reproductive, information-receptive,

research, partial search and the method of problem presentation, but at the same time the content of the educational material is revealed in a certain logical way - inductively or deductively. Therefore, we can talk about an inductively or deductively constructed conversation, a problem-based and deductively constructed story. O.N. Kiseleva classifies deductive methods as explanatory and illustrative, the method of problematic presentation of new material, and the method of independent study of new material from a textbook. To inductive - heuristic conversation, research method. One of the most important concepts in the concept of teaching methods is the concept of teaching methods. There is no single point of view on this concept. Some methodologists consider the technique to be part of the method, others consider it as a method that takes up little time in the lesson. We believe that reception should be considered as part of the method. For example, a teacher's story in a lesson is interpreted as a method for a long time, and as a technique for a short time. With this interpretation, it is difficult to distinguish method from technique. But the need for differentiation is obvious. The same techniques can be included in different methods. For example, the "filling out the table" technique. If the table is filled out at the direction of the teacher based on updating the students' knowledge, then this technique is included in the information-receptive method; if students establish new connections based on existing or previously studied patterns and make a table themselves, then this is a reproductive method; if the table is compiled on the basis of an independent search, it is a research method, and if we are talking about the help of a teacher, then this is a partial search method. Thus, table compilation as a technique serves several methods. When preparing for a lesson, the teacher plans learning (consolidation, repetition, control) using methods that should take into account the nature of the activity of both the teacher and the student. For example, it is advisable to organize the assimilation of types of subordinate clauses in a complex sentence with the help of a lecture (classification according to the source of knowledge - verbal method), students assimilate information in ready-made form

(classification according to the nature of cognitive activity - information-receptive method), a large volume of theoretical material is presented deductively (classification according to the method of presenting the material - deductive method). The teacher will use three methods at once when explaining the material in class. Subsequent consolidation of this topic will be carried out with the help of exercises (classification according to the source of knowledge - a practical method), involving the reproduction of the methods of activity shown by the teacher (classification according to the nature of cognitive activity - the reproductive method); consolidation proceeds according to the principle from the general to the specific (first the rule is learned, then exercises on this rule are performed - the deductive method).

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